

Prevalence of test anxiety among psychology students of SDCA

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Abstract

Last March 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic has halted and changed how individuals across the globe go about their daily lives. The pandemic has posed a significant threat not just economically and physical health, but also with the mental health of people across the globe. The unexpected switch from face-to-face classes to virtual/online learning has been proven a challenge to the students, as well as the educators and school administrators. Academic stressors such as academic demands, learning, performance and examination are the most common causes of stress and anxiety for college students, paired with the emerging problems brought upon by the pandemic, such as conflicting schedules, internet difficulties and learning environments. This specific type of performance anxiety is known as test anxiety. This study focused on the prevalence of test anxiety among selected psychology students. Data were obtained using the Google Forms Survey of the Westside Test Anxiety Scale. Results show that across all gender, the test anxiety level of the participants who identifies as homosexual fell on the extremely high test anxiety while male and female participants obtained scores that fell on high test anxiety range.

Keywords: Test anxiety, mental health, academic.

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Introduction

Last March 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic has halted and changed how individuals across the globe go about their daily lives. The pandemic has posed a significant threat not just economically and physical health, but also with the mental health of people across the globe. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the most vulnerable population for mental health-related concerns is those aged 15 to 29 years old. This age bracket includes college students who are in the midst of adjustments of online/virtual learning that results to stress and anxiety. Anxiety is a psychological disorder marked by tense feelings, worried thoughts, and bodily changes (Kowalski, 2000).

The unexpected switch from face-to-face classes to virtual/online learning has been proven a challenge to the students, as well as the educators and school administrators. Academic stressors such as academic demands, learning, performance and examination are the most common causes of stress and anxiety for college students, paired with the emerging problems brought upon by the pandemic, such as conflicting schedules, internet difficulties and learning environments. This has caused concern for throughout the academic community.

As stated previously, one of the common causes of anxiety for students is related to academic performance, which includes taking examinations. This performance – specific anxiety is known as test anxiety, which means a reaction to stimuli connected with an individual's experience of testing or evaluating situations (Sieber, 1980, as cited in Ping et. al, 2008).

According to Reyes and Castillo (2015), test anxiety is characterized by physiological changes, extreme stress and discomfort before, during, and/or after taking a test. Test scores are important in terms of academic and career development that is why students are under pressure to achieve high test scores resulting to increase test anxiety (Mohamadi et al., 2014). Mohamadi et al. (2014) stated that test anxiety can significantly affect the performance of the students.

In the Philippines, there are only a few studies related to test anxiety and its effect on the academic performance, as well as the mental health of the students. This is why this current study focused on identifying the test anxiety level of selected psychology students during the pandemic, as well as be a basis for a wellness program that will help alleviate the mental health issues experienced by the students.

Methodology

Participants

The current study has a total of 43 psychology students, consisting of seven (7) males, thirty-two (32) females, and four (4) homosexuals. The participants are all currently enrolled in St. Dominic College of Asia at the time of the data gathering. Informed consent were also obtained prior to answering the questionnaire.

Instrumentation

The participants were asked to answer the Westside Test Anxiety Scale (WTAS) via Google Forms Survey. The Westside Test Anxiety Scale (WTAS) is a self-report questionnaire that assesses anxiety impairment and cognitions related to performance. It is a 10-item instrument designed to identify the level of test anxiety of students (Driscoll, 2006). The Westside Test Anxiety Scale items are divided into two categories: performance impairment which includes memory loss and poor cognitive processing, and intrusive worry. There were no items included to measure physiological symptoms.

Scoring and administration of the Westside Test Anxiety scale has been validated by Richard Driscoll. Average score of 4.0-5.0 indicates extremely high test anxiety, 3.5-3.9 indicates high test anxiety, 3.0-3.4 moderately high test anxiety, 2.5-2.9 high normal test anxiety, 2.0-2.5 normal test anxiety, and 1.0-1.9 indicates comfortably low test anxiety.

Statistical Analysis

The data gathered were presented in tabular and graphical form to show the results. Descriptive statistics such as frequency mean and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to statistically analyzed the scores obtained from the participants. Frequency scores were included to indicate the number of participants per gender while mean scores were utilized to see the level of test anxiety of the participants. One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was also used to see if there are significant differences between the mean scores of the 3 gender categories.

Results

Figure 1. Frequency between gender groups

Figure 1 shows the number of participants in the current study according to their gender preference (male, female and homosexual). There are seven (7) males, thirty-two (32) females, and four (4) homosexuals who participated in the current study.

Table 1. Test anxiety mean score of the participants

Sex	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Male	3.9571	7	.56231
Female	3.7438	32	.78203
Homosexual	4.0750	4	.38622
Total	3.8093	43	.72171

Table 1 shows the mean scores of the respondents according to gender. All of the mean scores across the sub-profiles yielded a result of 3.0 above, which means that the participants have been experiencing high test anxiety. Across the sub-profiles, homosexual individuals have the highest mean score (4.07) which means that participants from this demographic tend to have extremely high test anxiety compared to males (3.9) and females (3.7), both mean scores of the demographics interprets to high test anxiety.

Table 2. Test for significant difference between groups

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.573	2	.286	.538	.588
Within Groups	21.303	40	.533		
Total	21.876	42			

The table above shows the test for significant difference between groups (female, male, and homosexual). The computed p-value for the between groups ANOVA is greater than the .05

alpha level. This results indicates that there is no significant difference between the averages of each group.

Analysis and Discussion

Test anxiety is a universal phenomenon that most students experience, at one point in their academic experience. No matter how smart, well – prepared or confident a student is, all of them experience some level of anxiety when exams are due. Normal amount of anxiety can be helpful in motivating students to study hard and prepare well for their exams, however, it becomes debilitating when it adversely affects the performance of the students, as well as their mental health. If students have high levels of test anxiety, they may experience physiological symptoms such as rapid heart rate, shallow breathing, tremors, among others. They may also experience intrusive worry and performance impairment.

Based on the statistical results above, all students, regardless of their gender identity, have experienced test anxiety. It is also important to note that the level of test anxiety that the students have fell on the extremely high and high test anxiety range. The results of this study shows that the test anxiety experienced by the participants may be caused by a number of factors, one of which is the immediate switch from face to face classes to virtual/online class. If not managed properly, test anxiety can develop into other types of mental health concerns, issues, or even disorders. According to Downs of Brown University, there are ways to manage test anxiety which includes letting go of perfectionism and preparing for the exam.

Psychologists Ross and Driscoll (2008) also provided basic framework for treatment of test anxiety which targets four areas: skill development, behavioral interventions, cognitive factors, and stress and lifestyle issues. School administrators and educators may be influential in terms of helping students alleviate the effects of test anxiety.

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